

COGNITIVE AND LINGUOCULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF METAPHORS

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: Metaphors are symbols that people use to describe things differently. They are found in all languages and they play an important role in language development. Metaphor is one of the main stylistic tools, especially in the analysis of fiction. In this article, we will consider different ways of using metaphors, as well as their cognitive and linguistic-cultural properties and their influence on language development.

Keywords: metaphor, conceptual metaphor, concept, linguocultural, lingvokulturrema.

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КОГНИТИВНО-ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ МЕТАФОР

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Abstract: Метафоры – это символы, которые люди используют для описания вещей по-разному. Они есть во всех языках и играют важную роль в развитии языка. Метафора является одним из основных стилистических средств, особенно при анализе художественной литературы. В данной статье мы рассмотрим различные способы использования метафор, а также их когнитивные и лингвокультурологические свойства и их влияние на языковое развитие.

Keywords: метафора, концептуальная метафора, концепт, лингвокультура, лингвокультурема.

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METAFORALARNING KOGNITIV HAMDA LINGVOMADANIY XUSUSIYATLARI

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Abstract: Metafora - bu odamlar narsalarni boshqacha tasvirlash uchun foydalanadigan belgilar. Ular barcha tillarda uchraydi va ular til rivojlanishida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Metafora, ayniqsa, badiiy adabiyotni tahlil qilishda asosiy stilistik vositalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada biz metaforalardan foydalanishning turli usullarini, shuningdek, ularning kognitiv va lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari hamda ularning til rivojlanishiga ta'sirini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Keywords: metafora, konseptual metafora, konsept, lingvomadaniy, lingvokulturrema.

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INTRODUCTION

Since the ancient history of the development of linguistics, the attitude towards the interpretation of metaphors has been different according to its philosophical analysis, and it has been analyzed mostly according to the grammatical, semantic, lexical and stylistic aspects of the metaphorical mechanisms. In modern linguistics, the characteristics of metaphors related to thinking and the human factor, based on the interpretation of anthropocentric paradigms, are put in the center of attention. Issues of language and thinking are a priority factor in determining the mechanism of formation of new ideas related to cognitive processes in the human mind. It is known that these issues are especially evident in the linguistic and cultural aspects of languages.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

N.Arutyunova, M. Black, P. Riquior, E. Cassirer, R. Jakobson and E. McCormack conducted scientific research on the philosophical-theoretical basis of metaphors, their logical analysis, their differences from similes, ornamental, praxeological features, and their philosophical paradigm. Also J. Lakoff, M. Johnson, Ye. Gogonenkova, Ye. Akishina, N. Charbonel, G. Ermolenko, I. Polozova, M. Merleau-Ponty, V. Pustovalova, D. Montminy, Ye. Reshetnikova, Ye. Malishkin and D. Ashurova on the cognitive, pragmatic, linguistic and cultural aspects of conceptual metaphor. Uzbek linguists Sh.Rakhmatullayev, M.Mirtojiyev, M.Mamadaliyeva and G.Qabuljonova researched the national-cultural, linguistic, semantic and cognitive features of metaphor based on the material of the Uzbek language.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article discusses the structure and forms of conceptual metaphors, their linguistic significance and their role in language development. Their cultural and cognitive characteristics are widely covered on the basis of examples. The meaning of conceptual metaphors of two languages (Uzbek and English) in the linguistic discourse and translation process is analyzed on the basis of wide-scale images.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is known that theoretical views about metaphors existed in ancient times. "Metaphor is the most active phenomenon of derivative meaning. According to linguistics, it is based on the fact that the originator and the referents of the derived meaning are similar to each other."¹⁸² In the last quarter of the last century, the idea that this phenomenon, which is one of the common ways of transferring meaning, occupies the main place in human cognitive activity, is being put forward. The study of metaphors created by famous scientists J. Lakoff and M. Johnson caused a radical change in the views on this matter. Metaphors serve as a unique mechanism of poetic image and rhetorical growth for people. Also, metaphors are considered as a unique decoration of language rather than a product of thinking and cognitive activity. But in everyday life it turns out to be the opposite. Therefore, metaphors are not only a linguistic phenomenon, but also form the main and integral part of human thinking and cognitive activity. J. Lakoff and M. Johnson: "Metaphors permeate not only everyday life, not only language, but also our thinking and activities. "Our everyday conceptual system is also metaphorical in its essence," he said."¹⁸³ The frequent occurrence of metaphors in human speech requires that this mechanism should be studied on the basis of a certain system or system. That is why scientists analyze them into separate systems and call them "metaphorical concepts" or "conceptual metaphors". The analysis of examples served as an important source in creating the essence of this concept. In particular, the formation of some abstract concepts such as "love", "love", "science", "happiness", "trust" and "war" in human thinking based on the source of information is closely related to the process of metaphorization.

According to the theory of cognitive metaphors, the process of interaction between knowledge structures (frames and scenarios) is based on metaphorization. According to J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, the content that is not explicitly expressed in the verbal structure is created on the basis of knowledge about frames."¹⁸⁴ Currently, the theory of cognitive metaphors has been applied to many fields and is one of the effective methods of knowledge, categorization, conceptualization, evaluation and explanation of the world. Also, since cognitive metaphors are the product of the thinking of the representative of each nation, the linguistic and cultural heritage and traces of that nation are also hidden in them. That is, the harmony of language and culture is clearly visible in the concepts forming each conceptual metaphor. Such peculiarities require great knowledge and skill from the translator in the process of translation. When comparing linguistic and cultural units or translating them from one language to another, it is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of the culture of that time, in particular, the folk

¹⁸² Mirtojyev M. O`zbek tili semasiologiyasi.-Toshkent: Mumtoz so`z,2010-B.94

¹⁸³ Lakoff J, Jonson M . Metaphors we live by. Chicago, IL: The University of Chicago Press.

¹⁸⁴ Будаев Э.В. Метафора в политической коммуникации : монография. М, 2008.

oral creativity. For example, since in the Uzbek translation, cunning is formed through the image of "bald man" and not the traditional "fox", in this case it is necessary to pay attention to the period requirement of authenticity. In modern times, it is traditional to compare cunning and cunning to the character of a fox, but in the Uzbek literature of the past, in particular, in folklore, this character was compared to "bald foxes".¹⁸⁵

J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, the authors of the theory of conceptual metaphors, divided them into three groups, i.e. orientational metaphor, ontological metaphor, and structural metaphor. Orientational metaphors mean that figurative expressions in people's thinking refer to a certain place or direction. In the metaphor of happiness is up, sad down, happiness is up and sadness is down, which in Uzbek means head to the sky it is enough, it is used in metaphors. Ontological metaphors are the next type of conceptual metaphors, which ensure the transformation of abstraction into existence. Ideas are objects. By structural metaphors, it is possible to understand the formation of another meaning of a word through a complex systematic concept existing in human thinking. Love is a journey.

CONCLUSIONS

It became clear from the studies that modern linguistics pays great attention to the cognitive aspects of metaphors. Therefore, a person's long-term life experience, national-cultural values, historical experiences and geographical location play an important role in the formation of metaphors. This move, which serves to increase the effectiveness and expressiveness of speech, creates a number of complications for foreign language learners and translators. For this reason, the cognitive approach to the translation of metaphors allows us to see them as a product of human thinking and cognitive activity, as cognitive constructions that conceptually express it.

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